

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14634746>

Dorosh-Kizym M.

Associate Professor
Stepan Gzhytskyi National University
of Veterinary Medicine and Biotechnologies Lviv
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5680-6669>

Grabovskiy R.

Associate Professor
Stepan Gzhytskyi National University
of Veterinary Medicine and Biotechnologies Lviv
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5701-6199>

Dorosh M.

Senior Teacher
Lyceum «European» of the Lviv City Council
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3975-1229>

TRANSFORMATION OF UKRAINE'S AGRICULTURAL SECTOR IN THE CONTEXT OF MILITARY CONFLICT: CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

JEL Classification: O 330

SECTION "ECONOMICS": Економіка

Анотація. Метою цієї статті є аналіз сучасного стану сільського господарства України та вивчення проблем, що виникли внаслідок початку повномасштабної війни з російською федерацією. Важливим аспектом є оцінка впливу військового конфлікту на аграрний сектор, зокрема на пошкодження сільськогосподарських земель, інфраструктури та знищення виробничих потужностей. Окрім того, дослідження охоплює питання зростання вартості виробництва, проблеми з постачанням ресурсів, а також труднощі, з якими стикаються аграрії в умовах війни. Стаття також має на меті оцінити заходи, які були прийняті для збереження продовольчої безпеки, а також розглянути перспективи відновлення та адаптації аграрного сектору до нових умов.

Агропромислова галузь України, яка до початку військового вторгнення мала стратегічне значення для економіки країни, зазнала значних змін у результаті збройного конфлікту. Війна не лише порушила традиційні ланцюги поставок, але й призвела до масштабних руйнувань інфраструктури, що ускладнило ведення сільського господарства в багатьох регіонах. В умовах військового конфлікту сільське господарство стало однією з основних цілей ворога, що намагається знищити або контролювати продовольчі потоки, а також використати природні ресурси для досягнення своїх стратегічних цілей. Знищення або пошкодження агропромислових об'єктів, складських приміщень, а також припинення постачання сільськогосподарської техніки та добрив суттєво ускладнили продовження виробництва. Однак, попри всі труднощі, українські аграрії продовжують боротьбу за збереження та відновлення виробничих потужностей, намагаючись мінімізувати наслідки війни для продовольчої безпеки як на національному, так і на міжнародному рівнях.

Агропромисловий сектор займає важливе місце в економічній структурі України, виступаючи основним рушієм не лише для сільських територій, але й для розвитку

національної економіки в цілому. До початку повномасштабної війни щорічне зростання цієї галузі становило 5-6%, а частка сільськогосподарського виробництва у валовому внутрішньому продукті досягала 10%, разом із переробкою сільськогосподарської продукції – 16%.

Сільське господарство України посідало провідні позиції в світовому виробництві окремих видів продовольства, забезпечуючи до 6% від загального обсягу світового споживання калорій. Україна була лідером у міжнародній торгівлі соняшниковою олією (перше місце у світі), ріпаком та ячменем (третє та четверте місця відповідно), а також іншою сільськогосподарською продукцією. Торгівля сільськогосподарськими товарами приносила Україні близько 22 млрд доларів США щорічно, що становило 41% загального обсягу експорту. Розвиток індустріального сільськогосподарського виробництва в Україні дозволяв знижувати вплив різниці в рівнях державної підтримки та вартості кредитування у порівнянні з країнами Північної Америки та Європейського Союзу, що сприяло успішній конкуренції на міжнародних ринках. Залучення максимальної кількості сільськогосподарських земель призвело до завершення етапу екстенсивного розвитку та поступового переходу до інтенсивного зростання, що базувався на покращенні технологій виробництва, виготовленні продукції з вищою доданою вартістю, оновленні технічного парку та будівництві сховищ, а також розвитку переробної промисловості.

На сьогоднішній день близько 5% земель сільськогосподарського призначення зазнали пошкоджень внаслідок збройного конфлікту. Втрати доступних для посіву площ перевищують 25%, зрощуваних земель – понад 70%, площ під ягодами становлять близько 25%, під садами – близько 20%.

Внаслідок зростання цін на добрива, паливе та насіння, відбулося значне збільшення вартості виробництва сільськогосподарської продукції. Крім того, велика частина земель наразі є небезпечною для ведення сільськогосподарських робіт через пошкодження та мінування територій. Значних руйнувань зазнали також і ключові інфраструктурні об'єкти, зокрема сільськогосподарські, складські, транспортні, енергетичні та переробні підприємства.

Annotation. The purpose of this article is to analyze the current state of agriculture in Ukraine and examine the problems that have arisen due to the onset of the full-scale war with the Russian Federation. An important aspect of the study is the assessment of the impact of the military conflict on the agricultural sector, specifically the damage to agricultural land, infrastructure, and the destruction of production capacities. Additionally, the research addresses issues such as the rising cost of production, resource supply problems, and the difficulties faced by farmers in wartime conditions. The article also aims to evaluate the measures taken to ensure food security and explore the prospects for the recovery and adaptation of the agricultural sector to the new circumstances.

The agro-industrial sector of Ukraine, which had strategic importance for the country's economy prior to the outbreak of the military invasion, has undergone significant changes as a result of the armed conflict. The war not only disrupted traditional supply chains but also led to large-scale destruction of infrastructure, which complicated agricultural activities in many regions. In the context of the military conflict, agriculture became one of the main targets of the enemy, who sought to destroy or control food flows, as well as exploit natural resources to achieve their strategic objectives. The destruction or damage of agro-industrial facilities, warehouses, as well as the disruption of agricultural machinery and fertilizer supplies, significantly hindered the continuation of production. However, despite all the challenges, Ukrainian farmers continue to fight to preserve and restore production capacities, trying to

minimize the consequences of the war for food security both at the national and international levels.

The agro-industrial sector occupies an important place in Ukraine's economic structure, acting as a key driver not only for rural areas but also for the development of the national economy as a whole. Before the full-scale war, the annual growth of this sector was 5-6%, and the share of agricultural production in the gross domestic product reached 10%, with agriculture and food processing combined accounting for 16%.

Ukraine's agriculture held leading positions in the global production of certain types of food, providing up to 6% of the world's total caloric consumption. Ukraine was a leader in the international trade of sunflower oil (ranking first globally), rapeseed, and barley (ranking third and fourth, respectively), as well as other agricultural products. The trade in agricultural products brought Ukraine about 22 billion USD annually, accounting for 41% of the country's total exports. The development of industrial agricultural production in Ukraine allowed for reducing the impact of disparities in government support levels and the cost of financing compared to North American and European Union countries, contributing to successful competition in international markets. The involvement of the maximum amount of agricultural land led to the completion of the extensive growth phase and the gradual transition to intensive growth, based on improvements in production technologies, the manufacturing of higher value-added products, updating the machinery fleet, building storage facilities, and developing processing industries.

Currently, about 5% of agricultural land has been damaged as a result of the armed conflict. The loss of available arable land exceeds 25%, with more than 70% of irrigated land affected, around 25% of berry plantations, and about 20% of orchards.

Due to the rising prices of fertilizers, fuel, and seeds, the cost of agricultural production has significantly increased. Furthermore, a large portion of the land is now dangerous for agricultural activities due to damage and landmines. Significant destruction has also occurred to key infrastructure facilities, including agricultural, storage, transport, energy, and processing industries.

Keywords: rural entrepreneurship, logistics, infrastructure, land resources, GDP, raw materials, resilience, energy supply, diversification, ecosystems, agriculture, exports, grain, food security, war, economy, global market, ports, recovery, sustainable development, losses, production, climate-smart agriculture, innovation.

Introduction

The issue of Ukraine's economic development during wartime, as well as the consequences and challenges faced by the country, has been addressed in the scientific works of a number of domestic economists, including Bila I.S., Blyzniuk V.V., Venger V.V., Horbach L.M., Iliukhina V.V., Kovalychuk N.O., and others. Special attention was given by the scholars to the problems of agriculture, which has become one of the most vulnerable sectors of the economy during the war. In particular, the studies focused on the damage to agricultural infrastructure, the destruction of agricultural land and equipment, as well as the impact of rising resource costs on agricultural production. This topic has also been the subject of research and publications by various public and private institutions, including the National Institute for Strategic Studies, the Institute of Economics and Forecasting of the NAS of Ukraine, as well as agricultural research centers and organizations dealing with food security and the restoration of agricultural production in wartime conditions.

The purpose of the article. Given the significant losses and damage, the agricultural sector requires a comprehensive approach to recovery, including financial support, infrastructure reconstruction, and the modernization of agricultural enterprises. It is necessary to develop strategies for maintaining and improving

food security at the national level, particularly through the creation of reserves and the development of alternative supply routes for resources.

Results

The full-scale military invasion of Russia into Ukraine has created new conditions for the functioning of the country's agricultural sector. The challenges arising from this situation demand the introduction of modern approaches and adaptive solutions to ensure its efficiency in the new realities.

Historically, Ukraine has played a key role in ensuring global food security, possessing a significant volume of agricultural product exports. Prior to the war, Ukraine was one of the top five global exporters of grain, sending approximately 75% of its agricultural output to external markets. Domestic consumption of grain, by contrast, accounted for only 20-25%. Specifically, Ukraine contributed roughly 10% of global wheat exports, over 14% of corn, and more than 47% of sunflower oil. According to expert estimates, in 2021, Ukraine's contribution to the global food market provided food for around 400 million people [4].

Ukraine's role in supplying grain to the United Nations World Food Program (WFP), which feeds about 120 million people worldwide suffering from food shortages, was particularly significant. However, the war and the blockade of Ukrainian ports severely limited the ability to export grain, leading to a multiple-fold increase in global prices. For example, according to the Kyiv School of Economics, wheat prices increased by 26% in just the first week of the war. This caused substantial damage to the economies of countries in Africa and Asia, where budgets often depend on the availability of imported food [3].

The Russian aggression has had a profound impact on Ukraine's ability to maintain the stability of agricultural product exports, creating new challenges for both the domestic economy and the global food system.

To ensure the resilience of the agricultural sector during the war and its effective recovery after hostilities cease, it is crucial to focus on aspects such as inclusive agricultural development, support for rural entrepreneurship, and the expansion of multi-sectoral economies. Additionally, it is necessary to rethink Ukraine's role in the global food system, promote the transition to climate-smart agriculture, and develop the sector based on sustainable development principles. This implies creating conditions in which economic growth and the fulfillment of societal needs occur without harming ecosystems or the viability of future generations [3].

The military actions initiated by Russia have caused significant losses to Ukraine's real economy, destroying assets, production and logistical chains, infrastructure, as well as agricultural and land resources. According to expert assessments, by early September 2023, the total amount of direct losses was 151.2 billion USD, with 11.4 billion related to industry and 8.7 billion to the agribusiness sector and land resources. As a result, the share of the real sector in GDP structure significantly decreased, from 26.6% in 2021 to 19.7% in 2022 [5].

Despite these challenges, signs of recovery in the real sectors were observed in 2023. This was made possible by domestic demand for products to support the armed forces, infrastructure restoration efforts, stable energy supply, business relocation, and diversification of export routes.

However, the development of the real economy remains reliant on the use of resource and geographical advantages, while the scientific and technological potential remains insufficiently integrated. This approach reinforces the economy's reliance on raw materials and limits opportunities for creating added value through resource processing within the country and integrating innovations [7].

Agriculture, being the backbone of Ukraine's economy before the war, continues to play a key role in ensuring food security even during wartime and will remain an essential element of post-war recovery. However, the existing model of the agricultural sector has shown its vulnerability, based on the scale of production, raw material orientation, and a distorted structure. Large agricultural enterprises primarily focus on crop production, while small farmers and households are responsible for labor-intensive production, including livestock and fruits and vegetables. In 2022, household farms produced 34.8% of total agricultural output, including 43.9% of livestock products and 32.3% of crop products (fig. 1.) [11].

SOURCE: STATISTICAL YEARBOOK OF UKRAINE 2023

Households remain the main producers of labor-intensive products, holding over 70% of cattle and producing the majority of vegetables, fruits, and berries. In 2022, the share of family farms in total agricultural output was only 11.2%, highlighting the need for changes to strengthen their role in the country’s agricultural system.

Global experience shows that small and medium-sized enterprises, particularly family farms, are the backbone of the agricultural sector in countries with developed market economies. These farms are characterized by simplified registration, accounting, and reporting procedures, as well as receiving significant tax benefits and government support. According to FAO, more than 83% of global livestock production and 51% of crop production comes from family farms. In the European Union, about 85% of farms are family-run, managing approximately 70% of agricultural land [4].

Amid the war, Ukraine’s economic recovery requires addressing urgent issues, scaling up successful business strategies, and adapting to new conditions. Of particular importance is building the real sector based on modern technologies that will ensure structural transformation of the economy, with an emphasis on the development of processing industries. Additionally, integrating principles of sustainable development, energy efficiency, circular economy, and environmentally clean production is crucial, aligning with European approaches to ensuring competitiveness [7].

For sustainable economic development during the war and post-war recovery, it is necessary to develop conceptual, instrumental, and applied components. This will enable effective responses to existing challenges while leveraging potential opportunities.

The war has caused significant losses to Ukraine’s agricultural sector. The most considerable damage to producers has come from the destruction of agricultural machinery (over 4.65 billion USD), the destruction and theft of products (1.87 billion USD), and the damage to production capacities (1.33 billion USD). According to World Bank estimates, indirect losses to the agricultural sector during the year of war amounted to 31.5 billion USD. The main part of these losses (46%) is linked to the reduction in domestic prices for export-oriented crops such as wheat, barley, corn, and sunflower [8].

FAO data indicates that by the end of 2022, rural households in Ukraine had lost approximately 2.25 billion USD, with losses in crop production amounting to 1.26 billion USD and in livestock production to 0.98 billion USD. At the same time, 25% of agricultural households ceased or reduced their production, with this figure reaching 38% in frontline regions [4].

As of October 2023, 84% of agricultural enterprises located in temporarily occupied areas had suspended their operations. In total, 38% of agricultural sector enterprises were not operating, and 45% were functioning at less than half of pre-war productivity levels.

In 2022, the number of active enterprises in agriculture, forestry, and fishing decreased by 31.4%, the largest decrease since 2012. This reduction in enterprises fell from 51.8 thousand to 35.6 thousand, surpassing the corresponding decline in the overall economy (-29.6%). At the same time, the number of individual entrepreneurs declined by only 11.3%. Specifically, the number of enterprises engaged in crop production decreased by 31.2%, perennial crops by 31.1%, livestock by 28.9%, mixed farming by 37.7%, and auxiliary activities by 32.8% [5].

By enterprise classification, the number of medium-sized enterprises decreased by 19.5%, large ones by 20.4%, small ones by 31.8%, and microenterprises by 34.5%. Despite this, Ukrainian agrarians continue to supply the domestic market with food products, increasing the production volumes of major crops.

In 2023, the production of cereals and legumes reached 57.6 million tons, oilseeds 20.7 million tons, and sugar beets 11.8 million tons. Despite a decrease in sown areas by 980 thousand hectares, cereal yields in 2023 increased to almost a record level of 55.0 c/ha, providing a 10% growth compared to 2022.

Vegetable production also increased: areas for onions grew by 8.1%, carrots by 6.1%, cabbage by 1.7%, beets by 7%, and potatoes by 2%. The total vegetable harvest reached 29 million tons, with potatoes accounting for 21.2 million tons. Dnipropetrovsk region led vegetable harvesting (780 thousand tons), while some regions achieved record tomato, cabbage, and cucumber harvests.

Production of melons, including watermelons (214 thousand tons) and melons (69 thousand tons), also showed positive dynamics. However, the shortage of vegetable storage facilities, with a deficit of about 150-170 units, forced farmers to sell their harvest at lower prices (tabl. 1) [11].

Table 1

**Average prices of agricultural products in Ukraine sold by enterprises for the period
2000-2023, UAH per ton**

Indicators	Years									
	2000	2005	2010	2015	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Cereal and leguminous crops	443,8	417,8	1120,9	2912,1	4315,0	3867,5	4794,1	6296,1	6399,8	5675,5
Including also										
Wheat	487,0	415,2	1085,8	2796,2	4586,1	4077,1	5017,5	6433,6	6097,6	5343,1
Rye	468,8	317,2	792,7	2222,4	3205,5	4276,8	4594,3	4470,5	4746,2	4080,3
Maize	386,4	343,1	1246,1	2989,9	4011,5	3684,6	4668,6	6245,5	6555,5	5868,7
Barley	374,2	488,5	955,1	2661,5	4815,4	3932,5	4352,7	5862,6	5632,8	5200,9
Oats	345,6	334,2	766,8	2065,4	3906,1	4305,6	4649,6	4948,1	5343,9	5897,0
Millet	349,9	295,4	1036,2	3315,8	7700,2	6929,5	5974,6	6559,0	7238,2	8240,8
Buckwheat	748,0	883,8	3910,0	9098,3	5827,8	7158,7	14550,8	17909,2	23805,4	12977,0
Rice	707,7	1017,9	2348,1	7426,3	7909,4	7898,7	8663,6	9007,7	13145,2	25671,8
Leguminous crops	575,0	579,0	1596,4	5382,5	5394,5	5337,4	6224,1	8264,6	8029,8	8030,4
Oilseeds	525,7	981,5	2942,6	7531,5	9318,3	8321,2	10852,9	16418,5	15015,0	13072,6
Factory sugar beet	121,5	177,0	478,5	788,6	749,0	753,7	871,5	1164,1	1572,2	1635,4
Potato	517,1	685,2	2131,0	2436,3	3746,0	5474,7	5103,4	4993,4	4519,5	5617,2
Vegetable crops	572,1	1462,1	2551,6	3903,4	4448,0	4497,0	4437,1	4679,6	14025,0	11593,1
Fruit and berry crops	394,9	987,8	2419,8	5894,5	5054,0	6494,4	9140,2	8177,1	8126,4	12531,5
Grapes	724,5	1476,1	3638,2	6450,3	5822,3	5451,4	6739,0	7211,9	7320,6	8269,9

Agricultural animals (in live weight)	2358,0	6909,9	10797,1	21966,2	33331,2	32679,8	32490,6	37380,5	45676,9	53186,6
Milk	536,4	1126,9	2938,7	4347,3	7602,4	8198,2	8839,9	10300,7	10969,0	12234,4
Eggs, in thousand pieces	191,7	251,8	470,6	1333,2	1600,3	1206,1	1258,6	1877,3	2328,3	3047,1
Wool	3182,5	4441,4	4165,3	14216,7	23350,5	25027,3	12537,4	13528,7	8327,4	15183,9

Source: *Statistical Yearbook of Ukraine 2023*

The dairy industry is gradually recovering: in 2023, industrial milk production reached pre-war levels of 1.88 million tons, 7.6% more than the same period in 2022. Exports of dairy products increased by 9.7%, reaching 70.2 thousand tons, although their value decreased by 6.5% due to reduced global demand [8].

The full-scale war in Ukraine has caused significant damage to the country's livestock sector. More than 300 livestock farms have been damaged or destroyed, resulting in the death of approximately 7,000 head of cattle and 3.5 million poultry.

As of October 2023, the cattle population in Ukraine decreased by 8% compared to the same period last year, with the number of cows dropping by 7%. This reduction is observed in both agricultural enterprises and household farms, with the latter sector suffering the most due to difficulties accessing resources and ongoing hostilities (tabl. 2) [11].

Table 2

Livestock production by categories of farms for the period 2000-2023

Indicators	Years										
	2000	2005	2010	2015	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	
Enterprises of all categories											
Meat (in slaughter weight), thousand tons	1663	1597	2059	2323	2355	2492	2478	2438	2207	2240	
Including also											
Beef and veal	754	562	428	384	359	370	345	311	268	257	
Pork	676	494	631	760	703	708	697	724	659	638	
Poultry meat	193	497	954	1144	1259	1382	1405	1374	1253	1318	
Milk, thousand tons	12658	13714	11249	10615	10064	9663	9264	8714	7768	7430	
Eggs, million pieces	8809	13046	17052	16783	16132	16678	16167	14071	11922	11379	
Wool, tons	3400	3195	4192	2270	1908	1734	1573	1497	1237	1187	
Enterprises											
Meat (in slaughter weight), thousand tons	438	588	1134	1464	1534	1698	1704	1720	1608	1680	
Including also											
Beef and veal	305	154	105	94	88	102	85	78	81	85	
Pork	91	111	256	400	360	385	385	432	407	405	
Poultry meat	36	320	772	968	1085	1210	1232	1209	1119	1187	
Milk, thousand tons	3669	2582	2217	2669	2755	2728	2761	2768	2644	2810	
Eggs, million pieces	2977	6458	10249	9762	8900	9358	8913	7013	5786	5655	
Wool, tons	1311	692	710	314	236	200	146	151	94	117	
Household farms											
Meat (in slaughter weight), thousand tons	1225	1009	925	859	821	794	774	718	599	560	

Including also										
Beef and veal	449	408	323	290	271	268	260	233	187	172
Pork	585	383	375	360	343	323	312	292	252	233
Poultry meat	157	177	182	176	174	172	173	165	134	131
Milk, thousand tons	8989	11132	9032	7946	7309	6935	6503	5946	5124	4620
Eggs, million pieces	5832	6588	6803	7021	7232	7320	7254	7058	6136	5724
Wool, tons	2089	2503	3482	1956	1672	1534	1427	1346	1143	1070

Source: Statistical Yearbook of Ukraine 2023

At the same time, agricultural enterprises have shown greater resilience, thanks to the possibility of relocating farms to safer regions. This has allowed some areas, such as Zakarpattia, Kharkiv, and Lviv regions, to see an increase in the cattle population. These positive changes indicate a certain adaptability of the agricultural sector to the new realities of war, although the overall demographic situation in the industry remains negative.

Despite these challenges, Ukraine has the potential for recovery and development in the meat sector, particularly through an expected 4% increase in pork production compared to 2022. This may lead to growth in meat exports, considering the decline in domestic demand due to population migration and the rising demand in global markets. For example, by the end of the first nine months of 2023, pork exports nearly doubled compared to the previous year.

However, the war has severely impacted Ukraine's food security, particularly due to the destruction of infrastructure, disruption of logistical chains, and reduced food production. At the start of the war, there was a shortage of products in local markets, but government measures quickly helped restore market functions. However, the situation in areas near the front line remains critical.

The instability in the financial sector has significantly complicated the operations of agricultural producers. Due to a lack of investment and rising production costs, including increases in fuel and fertilizer prices, many enterprises have been forced to reduce production volumes. For example, mineral fertilizer usage in 2023 decreased by 50-60% compared to the previous year. Increased production costs have led to a 30-60% rise in the cost of agricultural crops, which is reflected in domestic prices [6].

Nevertheless, despite these difficulties, Ukraine's agricultural sector has considerable potential for recovery if adequate state measures are implemented to support resilience and adaptation to the new conditions.

A labor shortage in Ukraine's agricultural sector has become one of the significant issues caused by the war. As a result of the conflict, many workers in the agricultural sector have been forced to halt their activities or leave their homes. According to FAO data, more than 150,000 farmers and food system workers have been affected by the war or have been forced to migrate. Small farmers, particularly those growing seasonal crops, have been the most affected, as this sector provided employment and income to rural populations [9].

Forced migration and the conscription of men into the armed forces have led to a severe shortage of labor, which, in turn, has increased the workload on women. For many small producers, the prospects of resuming operations on their lands remain uncertain due to land contamination, landmines, destruction of equipment and infrastructure, and a lack of financial resources to restore their farms. This could lead to their exit from agriculture or a change in specialization.

The destruction of infrastructure for production and storage of agricultural products is another consequence of the war. Grain storage facilities, food warehouses, and logistics facilities, which were specifically targeted, have significantly complicated the export of Ukrainian grain, resulting in decreased revenues for agricultural producers. Problems with product storage due to power outages during the winter of 2022-2023 led to the spoilage of significant volumes of agricultural products. Currently, the total volume of destroyed grain storage facilities is 8.2 million tons, with 3.25 million tons damaged [10].

Additionally, due to the fighting and landmining, approximately 30% of fields became unsuitable for sowing in 2022, and this share decreased to 25% in 2023. High levels of soil contamination with harmful substances, metal fragments, and remains of explosive materials have made these lands unfit for agricultural use. Major losses were also caused by the destruction of the Kakhovka Hydroelectric Power Station, which inflicted significant damage to aquatic bioresources [6].

The negative consequences for the fishing industry became evident after the destruction of the Kakhovka HES: more than 11,000 tons of fish died, and 85 fish farms were destroyed. The loss of fish resources led to financial losses amounting to 9.8 billion UAH. The restoration of aquatic bioresources will require significant time, as the process of replenishing fish populations and feed resources is based on complex ecological cycles that recover gradually.

These destructions in the agricultural and fishing sectors have long-term economic consequences that require a systematic approach to recovery and support for agriculture at the state level.

According to the analytical report «Post Disaster Needs Assessment» (PDNA) prepared by the Government of Ukraine in collaboration with the UN, the World Bank Group, and the European Union, the damages to the agricultural sector due to the war are estimated at \$406.6 million. Significant losses have been caused by the breach of the Kakhovka Dam, which led to irrigation disruptions and crop losses amounting to 376.7 million. Flooded areas covered an area of 620 km², and 333,000 ha of protected and forested areas were damaged, along with 11,294 ha of corresponding areas. These changes also led to river contamination, affecting ecosystems and biocenoses [1].

According to PDNA, total losses in ecosystem services exceed 6.4 billion, accounting for 58% of all losses. The needs for ecological recovery are estimated at \$59.5 million, with key priorities being demining, cleaning, and assessing contaminated areas. Some of the environmental consequences are irreversible and may have a cascading effect on other sectors for decades.

Analyzing the research of scientists and experts, the most effective method for restoring agricultural lands is conservation, which involves removing the land from agricultural use and restoring natural ecosystems. In Ukraine, where nearly 78.2% of agricultural land was cultivated before the war, conservation could reduce this percentage and help increase the resilience of soils to erosion [9].

It is advisable to shift agricultural production towards growing drought-resistant crops under limited irrigation conditions. Growing crops such as millet and sorghum could be a promising direction since they do not require constant irrigation. However, for this to be feasible, farmers need to be provided with planting material, which is currently lacking.

Dryland farming, which does not involve irrigation, is another option for adapting to new conditions. The yield of such crops depends on rainfall, temperature, and other factors, so special agro-meliorative measures, such as the fallow method and contour plowing, are used.

Additionally, in wartime conditions, creating greenhouse farms and drilling wells to supply water to small farms can be considered. However, this approach is not a nationwide solution, as it cannot meet the needs of large agricultural areas and has limited application due to the presence of saline water in some regions, which could lead to soil salinization.

Various international aid and cooperation programs are being implemented to support agricultural producers and communities during the war. One important project is the USAID Agricultural and Rural Development Program (AGRO), which in 2023 provided farmers with the necessary seeds and fertilizers to process about 370,000 hectares of land. This helped grow over 110,000 tons of sunflower seeds and increased grain yields by 220,000 tons [1].

Support is also provided through the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), which implements two programs through the State Agricultural Register. One of them provides investment grants to small agricultural producers, cooperatives, and geographical indication producers, funded by the European Union. Another program supports rural households in areas affected by hostilities. Through this program, 5,000 families received free potatoes and seed kits for various crops (cabbage, radish, eggplant, onions, tomatoes, and others).

Another important initiative is the grant programs by the international humanitarian organization Mercy Corps, which supports agricultural businesses that have relocated their operations and farms affected by the war. These programs are funded through the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC) and cover Kyiv, Poltava, Sumy, and Chernihiv regions. Small and medium-sized businesses receive financial support to co-invest in modernizing processing capacities, product storage, and providing agricultural services. Recovery through these programs will help create new jobs for internally displaced persons (IDPs) and local residents [5].

These measures contribute to minimizing the negative impact of the war on the agricultural sector and create conditions for its recovery. An important direction for future state agricultural policy is increasing the resilience of the agricultural sector during the war and in the post-war recovery process.

The agricultural sector of Ukraine, during the full-scale war of 2023, demonstrated the ability to continue producing agricultural products and supplying food both domestically and to foreign markets. However, this occurred under conditions of significant financial losses, related to low prices for grain and oilseed crops on the domestic market, complicated exports, and limited opportunities to restore the material and technical base, infrastructure, and return to farming on land affected by the war. One of the most serious problems was the destruction of the Kakhovka Dam, which caused flooding of lands where agricultural activities could not be conducted [10].

A shift in the structure of sown areas towards the production of more profitable oilseeds helped partially cover the costs of agricultural producers. The overall increase in plant production volumes was made possible by favorable weather conditions. However, most livestock sectors, especially meat and dairy production, remain in a crisis state, particularly due to reduced production in household farms.

The main directions for the development of the agricultural sector during the war should focus on maintaining the effectiveness of the «production – processing – storage – food supply» chain. It is crucial to increase agricultural production, create new (temporary) facilities for storage and primary processing, and attract public and private resources to supply food to distribution points [5].

In the post-war recovery phase, it is necessary to promote the diversification of agricultural production, increase the capitalization and investment attractiveness of agribusinesses, and create market institutions to enhance the efficiency of agricultural resource use. This will strengthen food security, support the development of a multi-sectoral economy, and increase the export of goods with higher added value.

Increasing production in the agricultural sector should not be an end in itself. Production growth should not only ensure food security but also create conditions for the development of other sectors of the economy and for the implementation of development goals in rural areas.

Ukraine's status as a candidate country for EU membership could become an important milestone in the development of the agricultural sector and small agribusinesses. The EU integration processes not only change the format of relations between Ukraine and the EU but also set strategic guidelines for systemic economic reforms in the agricultural sector, especially for small agricultural entities, which are the foundation of rural life in the country [8].

During the full-scale war, the agricultural sector of Ukraine continues to remain one of the main elements of the national economy, ensuring its stability and resilience.

Despite the significant losses caused by the aggressor, the sector is capable of not only ensuring internal food security but also supplying products to foreign markets. The ongoing transformations in the agricultural sector are contributing to a rethinking of the development strategies of economic entities, seeking new opportunities to increase domestic product processing and its realization. At the same time, it is important to adapt the export structure, focusing on increasing the share of processed agricultural products, which will reduce the likelihood of conflicts with partner countries, which mostly limit the import of raw agricultural materials, and mitigate the risks of vulnerability in Ukrainian agro-exports [2].

In addition to ensuring domestic consumption, Ukraine needs to form strategic food reserves for the long term. This will not only increase domestic demand for agricultural products but also serve as an important tool for economic stability and security.

The decline in the price of grain on the domestic market, caused by rising logistics costs, creates opportunities for the development of livestock farming. Cheaper and more accessible feed allows for the formation of local livestock clusters, reducing transportation costs and creating new jobs. To realize this potential, it is necessary to develop the capabilities of local enterprises involved in processing cereals into feed products, as well as create new mini-farms capable of producing meat and milk. This will also help maintain livestock in household farms and strengthen food systems locally [3].

A serious threat to the agricultural sector remains Russian attacks on energy infrastructure, but these attacks also stimulate the expansion of the use of bioenergy resources in agriculture. Improving the decentralization of energy production and using by-products of agriculture, such as biomass, can significantly enhance the energy resilience of communities and agribusinesses. This will also allow for the creation of new production capacities, for example, for growing early vegetables using local energy resources, which could compensate for losses of capacity in the southern regions of Ukraine. Additionally, the introduction of technologies for growing energy crops during land restoration after wartime contamination can contribute to the sustainable development of the agricultural sector [5].

The recovery of the agricultural sector is a key factor for the activation of adjacent industries, such as agricultural product processing, the food industry, fertilizer production, agricultural machinery, bioenergy, and the IT industry, which is actively implementing digitalization in agricultural production and logistics. These industries are expected to become more attractive for investment due to the improvement of the financial situation in the agricultural sector [3].

To achieve this, it is important to inform businesses about investment opportunities, systematize the needs of agribusinesses, and expand demand for products and services from related sectors. To optimize intersectoral interaction, it is necessary to create agro-food clusters, attract investments for the diversification of agribusinesses, and promote the localization of production in regions, which will reduce transportation costs and improve the competitiveness of domestic products.

The diversification of agricultural production in Ukraine, based on increasing the capitalization and investment attractiveness of agribusinesses, is an important step in the development of the agricultural sector. This involves attracting small and medium investors, which could form the basis for a new generation of producers, especially in the small-scale segment. These producers need the transfer of the latest technologies, skill development, and the ability to implement innovative methods of farming, which will significantly improve the sector's efficiency and competitiveness. Strengthening the links between the agricultural and industrial sectors will foster the development of integrated production chains, increase production capacity, and create new opportunities for the domestic market [10].

Together, these factors should form the foundation for enhancing Ukraine's agrarian resource potential, which could transform the agricultural sector into a driver of socio-economic development, focused on sustainable and inclusive growth.

These changes will enable the agricultural sector to become an important driver of structural modernization of the country's economy, reducing the gap in the quality of life between rural and urban residents. Priority areas also include the development of rural areas, where access to new technologies, resources, and opportunities for local communities will increase.

Adapting national legislation to European and international standards regarding crop cultivation, animal husbandry, and ensuring product quality and safety is an important step in Ukraine's integration into the global economy. This will allow the country to remain a reliable supplier of food to the global market, while increasing the export of products with higher added value [2].

In the long term, this policy will contribute to deepening cooperation with the European agricultural business, particularly through the development of new mutually beneficial initiatives and joint ventures, opening up prospects for further development of agriculture and integration into a unified European agricultural economy.

Conclusion

The agricultural sector of Ukraine, despite significant losses, continues to play a vital role in ensuring the country's food security. This highlights the sector's ability to adapt to the new realities of war and produce essential products for both domestic consumption and export. However, the recovery of this sector requires the implementation of innovative production methods, as well as active international aid and government support. In this context, it is crucial to create new temporary storage and primary processing facilities that will help maintain production levels, even amidst the unstable front-line situation.

Particularly relevant is the diversification of agricultural production, including a shift towards drought-resistant crops and the development of local agricultural clusters. Such approaches not only reduce dependence on traditional farming methods but also decrease risks associated with climate conditions and ongoing hostilities. The promotion of crop diversification and the integration of new technologies will be essential to the sustainable recovery of the sector. This transformation also implies a rethinking of the organization of agricultural markets, encouraging local production systems that are more resilient to external shocks, such as the ongoing conflict.

An essential aspect of recovery involves leveraging bioenergy resources, which provide opportunities to enhance energy resilience in rural areas and reduce dependence on conventional energy sources. The use of agricultural by-products, such as biomass, can significantly contribute to decentralizing energy production and fostering the growth of local energy capacities. Furthermore, the development of energy-efficient technologies for crop production in conflict-affected areas can help offset the losses of agricultural capacities in Ukraine's southern regions, making agricultural systems more sustainable in the long term.

At the same time, the European integration processes offer Ukraine an opportunity to modernize its agricultural sector by adopting European standards and practices, particularly in terms of product quality, safety, and sustainable farming methods. EU integration also sets strategic guidelines for systemic economic reforms, particularly in support of small and medium-sized agricultural enterprises, which are the backbone of rural life in Ukraine. The implementation of these reforms could strengthen Ukraine's competitive edge on international markets and foster cooperation with European agricultural businesses through joint ventures and mutually beneficial initiatives.

The establishment of strategic food reserves is another critical measure to ensure long-term food security. Such reserves would not only help stabilize domestic food markets but also act as a crucial tool for economic stability, mitigating the risks of food shortages and inflation. The diversification of agricultural production, which includes increasing the capitalization and investment attractiveness of agribusinesses, will be key to achieving this goal. Attracting small and medium investors, particularly in the small-scale segment, can lead to the emergence of a new generation of agribusinesses that will drive growth and enhance sectoral efficiency.

In the long term, strengthening the agricultural sector will also contribute to the activation of adjacent industries, such as agricultural product processing, the food industry, fertilizer production, agricultural machinery, and bioenergy. The integration of digital technologies into agricultural production and logistics will make these sectors more attractive for investment and help optimize the entire agricultural value chain.

These transformations should lay the foundation for enhancing Ukraine's agrarian resource potential, turning the agricultural sector into a driver of socio-economic development. This shift will not only promote inclusive growth but also reduce the economic gap between urban and rural populations, thereby fostering the long-term development of the rural economy. Moreover, adapting national legislation to international standards in agriculture will ensure Ukraine's continued competitiveness on the global market, enabling it to be a reliable supplier of high-quality agricultural products.

In conclusion, the adaptation of Ukraine's agricultural sector to the challenges posed by war, while maintaining its productivity, resilience, and capacity for innovation, will contribute to the country's sustainable recovery and integration into the global economy. This process, rooted in the effective use of new technologies, diversification of agricultural production, and strengthening of local markets, will help

build a more resilient agricultural system capable of meeting both domestic needs and international demands in the future.

Perspective directions of further research. In the context of Ukraine's agricultural sector, ongoing studies could delve into the dynamics of agricultural recovery and adaptation to the war's consequences, focusing on the economic resilience of agricultural enterprises in post-war conditions. Research could explore the transformation of production processes, including the shift towards crop diversification and increased reliance on sustainable agricultural methods, which would contribute to strengthening food security and improving the competitiveness of Ukrainian agricultural products on global markets. Furthermore, future investigations might emphasize the role of technological innovation and digitalization in agribusiness, including the introduction of smart farming technologies and the development of digital tools for agricultural logistics, which could enhance the efficiency of resource use, reduce operational costs, and foster more resilient agricultural systems.

Another important area for future research could involve examining the impact of international cooperation and external aid on agricultural recovery, evaluating the effectiveness of programs implemented by various organizations and their long-term effects on rebuilding agricultural infrastructure, developing human capital, and ensuring sustainable agricultural practices. Moreover, studying the potential of rural development strategies and local-level adaptation mechanisms could offer valuable insights into strengthening the social and economic fabric of rural areas, improving livelihoods, and reducing migration pressures.

Finally, an exploration of the regulatory and policy frameworks within Ukraine's agricultural sector, especially in terms of aligning national standards with European and global practices, could be crucial in understanding the pathways for integrating Ukraine into international markets, fostering foreign investments, and enhancing the long-term sustainability and resilience of the agricultural sector in the post-war era.

References

1. Bondarchuk N. V., Dziurakh Y. M. (2024). Public administration in conditions of war: strategies for ensuring food security. *The Actual Problems of Regional Economy Development*. 2 (20). P. 78-85. <https://doi.org/10.15330/apred.2.20>.
2. Dorosh-Kizym M., Yakhno T., Todoshchuk A., Nykonchuk V., Zhyvko M. (2024) Logistics Network Design System in Eu Through Modern Modelling Techniques: Establishing Strong Transport Links to Improve Foreign Economic Relations. *International Journal of Religion*. 5 (11). P. 282-293. <https://doi.org/10.61707/ayzdcf26>
3. Grabovsky R., Dadak O., Dorosh-Kizym M. (2022). Competitiveness of Ukrainian agriculture on foreign markets and ways to increase it. *Scientific Messenger of LNU of Veterinary Medicine and Biotechnologies. Series Economical Sciences*. 24 (100). P. 16-21. <https://doi.org/10.32718/nvlvet-e10003>
4. Kvasnii L., Paslavska B., Condra O., Sysyn G. (2024). Features of the food market in the conditions of war in Ukraine. *Scientific Bulletin of International Association of Scientists. Series: Economy, Management, Security, Technologies*. 3 (1). <https://doi.org/10.56197/2786-5827/2024-3-1-3>
5. Makaliuk I., Kashpurenko T., Barannikov M. (2023). Position of enterprises from the agricultural sector of ukraine in the conditions of war: financial and investment aspects. *Economy and Society*. (49). <https://doi.org/10.32782/2524-0072/2023-49-7>
6. Nehrey M., Taranenko A., Kostenko I. (2022). Ukrainian agricultural sector in war time: problems and prospects. *Economy and Society*. (40). <https://doi.org/10.32782/2524-0072/2022-40-38>
7. Stolnikovych H., Neiter R., Bohonos M. (2022). Food security in Ukraine in six months wars. Retrieved from https://kse.ua/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/1page_6-Months-Food-Security_ukr_mib_final.pdf.

8. Skydan O., Dankevych V., Garrett R., Nimko O. (2023). The state of the agricultural sector in Ukraine during wartime: The case of farmers. *Scientific Horizons*. 26(6). P. 134-145. <https://doi.org/10.48077/scihor6.2023.134>
9. Vytoptova V. (2024). Study of the state and problems of agriculture in Ukraine in wartime conditions. *Agrarian innovations. Economy*. No 23. P. 210-213. <https://doi.org/10.32848/agrar.innov.2024.23.30>
10. Nehrey M., Taranenko A. (2023). E-governance of the agricultural sector of Ukraine: state agrarian register. *Bulletin of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv. Economics*. 1 (1(222)). P. 113-119. <https://doi.org/10.17721/1728-2667.2023/222-1/14>
11. Державна служба статистики України. URL: <https://ukrstat.gov.ua>